

Stability of an atom: A Perspective

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Abstract:

In this paper, author has attempted to discuss about stability of an atom, by means of two fundamental forces of nature; one gravitational and another Columb's force.

Introduction:

We know that gravitational force between any two masses 'm1' and 'm2' seperated by distance 'd' is given by

$$F = \frac{G m_1 m_2}{d^2}$$

(Eqn:1) where G is gravitational constant.

Similarly the columb's interaction for any two charges is given by

$$F = \frac{K q_1 q_2}{d^2}$$

(Eqn:2) where K is Columb's constant.

For stability of an atom, gravitational force must be equal to columb's force, which means

$$\frac{G m_1 m_2}{d^2} = \frac{K q_1 q_2}{d^2}$$

(Eqn:3)

Since the distance between two particles, for both forces are same, term 'd' gets cancelled out, giving us

$$G m_1 m_2 = K q_1 q_2$$

Which gives,

$$m_1 m_2 = \frac{K}{G} q_1 q_2$$

(Eqn:4)

Since both K, and G are constant, the above equation 3 shows that, mass of particles of atom is propertional to their charges.

On putting the value of K and G, we get,

$$m_1 m_2 = \frac{8.988 \times 10^9}{6.67 \times 10^{-11}} q_1 q_2$$

which gives,

$$m_1 m_2 = 1.347 \times 10^{20} q_1 q_2$$

(Eqn:5)

which gives,

$$m_1 m_2 \propto q_1 q_2$$

(Eqn:6)

Conditions:

1. For same mass and charges, i.e. proton or electron,
 $q_1 = q_2 = q$, and $m_1 = m_2 = m$

Then from equation 6, mass is proportional to the square of the charge, which becomes as, $m^2 \propto q^2$

2. If by any means mass of charged particles, is equal to the charge of charged particles, then we obtain unit value (unity) from equation 5, which gives us constant being equal to 1, which is a contradiction.

Results and Conclusion:

From condition 2, it gives us evidently clear that, in theoretical perspective, mass of charged particle, doesn't equals to charge of charged particle, to explain the stability of an atom, where mass is proportional to the charge of particle.

Equation 5 can be written as

$$1.347 \times 10^{20} = \frac{m_1 m_2}{q_1 q_2}$$

Let us write the term 1.347×10^{20} as a constant G: (G-explosion) which is simply the ratio of Columb's constant, and Gravitational constant.

References:

Since both equations; Gravitational force, and columb's force are well known, author cites all fellow studying, and working in various fields of Physics.

Constant G-explosion (G: :) is introduced, to study experimental results, which is formed by calculation of two constants, as discussed above.